

Particle Transport in a Fluid interacting with an immersed Body with Alya

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Abstract

The Ocean Cleanup (www.theoceancleanup.com) is a foundation that develops technologies to extract plastic pollution from the oceans and prevent more plastic debris from entering ocean waters.

The main technology is the Ocean Cleanup Array which utilizes long floating barriers to capture and concentrate the plastic such that the system is a passive barrier. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is being used to study the catch efficiency debris of different sizes and densities, the transport of plastic along the containment boom, and the forces acting on it in order to determine the appropriate shape for their passive barrier concept. A study for the wave and boom influence on particle trajectories has to be done with CFD to investigate the effects of wind-and- wave- induced turbulence on the boom capture efficiently as well as to include the interaction between particles and the dynamic structure in the CFD analyses.

The objective of this PRACE project is to simulate the flow dynamic around the buoyancy body and the flexible skirt as well as the interaction of the plastic debris with the skirt. This simulation is a very strong multi-physics coupled problem carried out by Alya code: Navier-stokes equations in a turbulence regime, free surface, solid mechanics and particle Lagrangian transport have to be solved. On one hand, we have analysed the performance of the code solving this kind of complex problems in terms of computational efficiency. On the other hand, we have overcome the physical and numerical difficulties presented in the simulation.

1. Physical and numerical issues

In this project we face up to the difficulties related to the simulation of a multi-physic problem. In particular, we have solved the interaction between a structure and bi-fluid with the level set method to capture the interface between air and water. A particle transport immersed in this fluid is also solved.

Each component of the global problem has its own challenges to be overcome. This has been done with Alya code. Alya is organised in a modular way and is composed by kernel, services and modules. To solve a coupled

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multi-physics problem, all the required modules must be active and interacting following a well-defined workflow. Alya's kernel controls the run and contains the solvers, the input-output workflow and everything related to the mesh and geometry. There are modules to handle several different physical problems, and in the present simulation, the modules for the fluid flow problem to be used are *Nastin* and *Alefor*. *Nastin* has the physical description of the Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible fluids and *Alefor* provides the facility to deform the mesh of *Nastin*. Level module is in charge to solve the equation to track the free surface between air and water. For the solid mechanics problem, the module *Solidz* will be used and module *Partis* is the responsible to solve the trajectories of the particles. Kernel, modules and services have well-defined interfaces and connection points.

1.1 Turbulence

A sensitivity analysis has been performed in order to evaluate the sensibility of the different magnitudes like the position of the reattachment depending on some turbulence parameters of the RANS models.

We have tested 54 simulations varying the turbulence model, the mesh size and two input parameters: intensity turbulence and ratio viscosities, resulting in 9 different configurations detailed below.

Model = Spalart_almaras / K-W-sst
Mesh = 16491 elements/ 65964 elements/ 263856 elements
Resulting configurations = 1 / 2 / 3 / 4 / 5 / 6 / 7 / 8 / 9

Table 1: Configurations for intensity turbulence and ratio of viscosities

<i>Intensity_turbulence</i> <i>Ratio viscosities</i>	0.01	0.05	0.1
1.0	1	4	7
5.0	2	5	8
10.0	3	6	9

In Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 we show the global mesh and a zoom near the skirt for the three levels of refinement.

Figure 1: Details of mesh 1, the coarsest one

Figure 2: Details of mesh 2, medium level of refinement

Figure 3: Details of mesh 3, the finest one.

Reattachment in the interface: the position of the reattachment in the interface is depending mostly on the model and slightly on the mesh refinement. For the different parameters of intensity turbulence and ratio of viscosities the result is the same. As we can see in Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 where both turbulence models with 3 levels of refinement are compared for the configuration 1, 2 and 3 of the Table 1.

Figure 4: Position of the reattachment at configuration 1 for kw-sst and spalart turbulence model

Figure 5: Position of the reattachment at configuration 2 for kw-sst and spalart model

Figure 6: Position of the reattachment at configuration 3 for kw-sst and spalart turbulence model

In Figure 7 and Figure 8 we can prove that for the same turbulence model, the position of the reattachment is the same for different configurations (in this case are compared 1, 2 and 3 configurations).

Figure 7: Spalart turbulence model

Figure 8: kw-sst turbulence model

The resulting field of velocity and turbulence viscosity are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 9: Velocity field

Figure 10: Turbulence viscosity field

1.2 Free surface

The main challenge for solving time-dependent two-phase flow problems is to provide an accurate representation of the interface that separates the two different fluids. This involves the tracking of a discontinuity in the material properties like density and viscosity. In this project the level set method is used to tracking the moving interface. The level set equation is an hyperbolic equation of a smooth function $\Phi(\mathbf{x},t)$ which defines the position of the front by the isovalue $\Phi(\mathbf{x},t)=0$ such that $\Phi(\mathbf{x},t)>0$ corresponds to air domain and $\Phi(\mathbf{x},t)<0$ to water domain in our work. The main advantage of this approach is that the computational mesh does not have to conform to the interface. This implies that discontinuous integrals have to be computed because both viscosities and densities are discontinuous in all the elements crossed by the interface. The most common approach is to define a zone of thickness 2ϵ in the vicinity of the interface and to smooth the discontinuous density and viscosity over this thickness. This strategy may be the cause of two problems. One of them is the introduction of non-physical densities and viscosities in the smoothed region. The second problem is considered thickness constant. For ensuring that the smoothed region has a constant thickness, one has to reinitialize the level set so that it remains a distance function which implies a computational cost.

A local enrichment of the bases for the pressure is used in this work to improve the mass conservation properties in the elements cut by the interface avoiding the smoothing of the properties. The enrichment enables to capture discontinuous pressure gradient at the interface. A modified integration rule is used to ensure a good representation of the discontinuities in the cut elements. Figure 11 shows the enriched pressure used for an element crossed by the interface in a P1 element (left) and the integration rule (right).

Figure 11: Enriched pressure (left) and modified integration rule (right)

This strategy has been implemented for triangles, quadrilaterals, tetrahedral, hexahedra and pyramids. To validate the method the vertical channel benchmark test and cavity test of chapter 2 and 3 of the thesis [6] have been reproduced.

1.3 Wave generation

Another new ingredient implemented in Alya code to solve the problem has been the wave generator. This consists in a sector of the domain in which an analytical solution for the level set function is imposed and coupled with the numerical solution in order to generate a specific free-surface profile. This strategy is based in the work of reference [1].

To validate our free-surface model, 3-dimensional dam break problem has been carried out. Results are shown in Figure 12 and the experimental results come from the following reference [2].

Figure 12: Validation of a 3-dimensional dam break

1.4 Particles

Particles are transported solving the Newton's second law considering a series of forces: drag, gravity, buoyancy and friction. Friction force has been implemented in Alya in this project and regarding the particle-skirt interaction, a friction coefficient between 0.04 and 0.1 is considered. The time integration is based on the Newmark's method.

We are only considering a one-way coupling between fluid and particles such that the particles are transported by the fluid but have negligible effects on the fluid dynamics.

Figure 13 shows the trajectories of the particles immersed in the fluid flow.

Figure 13: Lagrangian transport of particles

1.5 Fluid-structure interaction

The barrier to capture the plastics is composed by a boom, skirt and ballast. The material of the boom is a neoprene, the skirt a spinnaker material properties and different weighs of the ballast have been tested.

Figure 14 shows the mesh of the fluid and solid domains in the initial configuration. In Figure 15 we can observe the deformed mesh of the solid.

Figure 14: Fluid-structure interaction. Mesh and initial condition

Figure 15: Fluid-structure interaction. Deformed configuration

2. Computational performance analysis

The parallelisation paradigm in Alya is a sub-structuring method, using a Master-Worker interaction model between the CPUs. Sub-structuring methods consist in distributing the work among the Workers, leaving the Master in charge of general tasks like I/O. The parallelisation of the fluid, solid and particle solvers is implemented with two levels of parallelism, MPI and OpenMP in order to introduce more parallelism.

In this section we present the performance of the multi-code approach to solve a coupled problem. In the Alya system it is possible to perform multi-code multi-physics simulations through its coupling capability [3] and [4], this means that different instances of the code can communicate between them and send relevant information to each other. Figure 16 represents a diagram of the workflow of the simulation. We can observe that three couplings are solved: *Nastin(nsi,ale)-Particles(pts)-Solidz(sld)*, explained in Section 1, through three instance of Alya: *Alya1*, *Alya2* and *Alya3* in the figure.

Figure 16: Diagram of the execution

Alya1 will be in charge of the fluid mechanics problem, *Alya2* of the solid mechanics problem and *Alya3* of particle transport. Then, the three codes will exchange relevant information to solve its own problem. The fluid mechanics code, will calculate and send the forces over the interface to the solid mechanics code and will receive from this the position of the interface. Particles receive from the fluid the velocity field in which the particles are immersed and transported.

This means that in one time step, the fluid mechanics problem is solved, the forces in the interface surfaces between fluid and structure calculated and sent to the solid mechanics code, who after deforming by the effect of these forces sends back the new position of the interface surface and the time step is advanced. At the same time, fluid mechanic problem sends the velocity field to the solver of trajectories of the particles. In Figure 16 the number of iterations of each solver and coupling are indicated in a red ball.

The resources between three physics are independent which is the critical point where dynamic load balance (DLB) is a very usefully tool. In this work we will use DLB (Dynamic Load Balancing Library). The DLB library aims at balancing applications with two levels of parallelism. Currently, the implemented modules balance hybrid MPI + OpenMP and MPI + OmpSs applications, where MPI is the outer level of parallelism and OpenMP or OmpSs are the inner ones. An important feature of the DLB library is that a runtime interposition technique is used to intercept MPI calls, as sketched in Figure 17. With this technique we do not need to modify the application, the DLB library is loaded dynamically when running the application to load balance the execution. The DLB library will load balance the MPI tasks redistributing the computational power in the second level of parallelism. This is done by changing the number of threads that each MPI task can use. It means that DLB will balance the load of the MPI tasks that are running in the same node (shared memory).

Figure 17: Sketch of DLB-MPI calls interaction

The main issue to be improved is the *efficiency*. The computational load is imbalanced and we have tried to solve this drawback. If we define *efficiency* as the rate between the summation of the times of each CPU and the maximum time multiplied by number of CPUs, this could be seen as the load balance, defined as the rate between the average time and maximum time. (The average time is defined as the summation of the times of each CPU and number of CPUs.). So, load imbalance implies losing efficiency.

The scaling behaviour of the code has not been modified in this work and we refer to the scalability of the code done by [5]. Alya has run efficiently up on up to 100,000 CPUs maintaining a scalability above 0.8.

In the distributed memory context in which Alya code is executed in this work the main difficult to be overcome is the unbalance problem due to the particles are concentrated in very few messages passing interface.

For this reason we have solved the problem using multi-code coupling between fluid and particle solver since independent partitions could be done for the fluid and particle computational domains. The coupling between solid and fluid mechanics is also done in two instances of codes because otherwise the implementation of the coupling is very invasive. In this coupling the main problem to be overcome is the asynchronism of the execution, this means, one solver has to wait the other.

Figure 18 shows a trace of an execution where we can observe the scenario mentioned before. The X-axis represents time and each horizontal line is a thread (grouped by MPI process). The trace has been obtained with the *Extrac* package [7] and visualised with *Paraver* [8].

Figure 18: Trace of an execution

As we mentioned before, a very useful strategy is a dynamic load balance applied at the shared memory level to fully exploit the available resources when MPI processes of the different solvers are idle. As we can see in Figure 18, particles and solid solvers have to wait until fluid has finished (black and red), as well as fluid has to wait to solid (purple). To improve the use of computational resources DLB has been applied to the execution. DLB has been enabled in the assembly of all the modules, subgrid scale for fluid solver and particles injections and solver. The experiments have been executed in Marenostrum III. Each node of this supercomputer is composed of 2×Intel Xeon processors (E5-2670), each of these two sockets includes 8 cores and 16 Gb of shared memory. The execution has been done with one node in order to illustrate how to optimise the resources on it.

Figure 19 shows the effect of using DLB in the resolution of our complex coupled problem. As we can see each MPI process is able to use more threads in some stages of the execution (originally only one thread was used for each process). In the right part of the figure we can see two histograms showing the number of CPUs used for useful computation in a given instant of time. In red the maximum capacity of the node is indicated and we observe how with DLB the use of the resources is closer to 16 which is the maximum number of CPUs available. So a more efficient use of the computational resources is achieved as well as shorter time to end the execution.

Figure 20 shows a zoom in assembly of the fluid where we can see how the processes performing the assembly are able to use the CPUs of the solid processes that are waiting for the force. This also is reflected in the histograms showing the number of CPUs used in this part of the execution.

The assembly of the solid is shown with detail in Figure 21. In this case the solid was originally running in 3 CPUs while the fluid was waiting for the displacement blocking in an MPI call 10 CPUs devoted to the execution of this instance of Alya. We can see with DLB the assembly of the solid can be performed in up to 13 CPUs.

Figure 19: Trace of an execution with DLB and histogram of use of the node

Figure 20: Trace of detail of a fluid assembly and histogram of use of the node

Figure 21: Trace of detail of a solid assembly and histogram of use of the node

The use of DLB is almost transparent, it is activated during the compilation. But as it relies on the OpenMP parallelization it must be activated with care. For this reason we have evaluated the potential of the tool used in this kind of problems activating it only in some parts of the code. We have observed significant benefit in the execution time in the parts of the application where DLB was activated.

Now that we have seen the potential in these kind of executions and problems we plan to extend its use to the whole simulation and evaluate its impact in the execution time.

3. Conclusions

We have simulated a very strong multi-physics problem which implies a huge challenge to be efficient and accurate.

In this project Alya code has been adapted in order to simulate the flow dynamic around the buoyancy body and the flexible skirt as well as the interaction of the plastic debris with the skirt. The main object is to estimate the boom's capture efficiency and make a proper design of the system composed by boom, skirt and ballast weight.

The work has been done in two directions. On the one hand, physical and numerical issues have been implemented and validated: pressure enrichment stabilization technique, improvement of integration in cut elements by the interface, waves generator, turbulence model and friction force. On the other hand, the computational performance of this complex coupled simulation has been analysed and optimised.

Alya code has demonstrated its high potential to face complex problems. The use of dynamic load balance library provides a very important gain in this kind of coupled problems in which the efficiency of the performance could be very poor. This project has been a great opportunity to applied high performance computing code, Alya, to industrial problem and has provided an excellent framework to obtain an instigator results to continue with the work. The use of DLB has been enabled in a few parts of the Alya code (i.e. the

assembly in both fluids and particles, the subgrid scale in fluids and the injection and computation of particles). Our aim was to evaluate the suitability of the approach and potential in this environment. As we have seen, the results are promising and as future work we will enable DLB in more parts of the code to finally use it during the whole execution. This would have a great impact in the efficient use of the computational resources.

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